

Appendix V

Computed Criticality Values

Goals	$C(G) = (\sum(\text{Weights})/\text{no. of stakeholders}) + S$
G1: Send messages to all pages' followers G2: Delete advertising messages	$C(G1) = 4+2/2 = 3$ $C(G2) = 5+3/2 = 4$ Thus, $C(G2) > C(G1)$
G3: Track people's data G4: Prevent all kinds of fraud and Be in charge of all the chatbots, or other automatic functions within the messenger	$C(G3) = 1+1/2 = 1$ $C(G4) = 5+3/2 = 4$ Thus, $C(G4) > C(G3)$
G5: Create individual ads G6: Use the same ads for all users	$C(G5) = 3+3/2 = 3$ $C(G6) = 5+2/2 = 3.5$ Thus, $C(G6) > C(G5)$
G7: Target non-brand-aware users G8: Restrict advertisers from doing extensive targeting	$C(G7) = 1+5/2 = 3$ $C(G8) = 5+2/2 = 3.5$ Thus, $C(G8) > C(G7)$
G9: Host webinars/online events G10: Want the app to be as basic as possible	$C(G9) = 1+2/2 = 1.5$ $C(G10) = 1+1/2 = 1$ Thus, $C(G9) > C(G10)$
G11: Avoid ad blockers G12: Block ads while playing games G13: Filter ads	$C(G11) = 1+5+5/3 = 3.6$ $C(G12) = 5+2+3/3 = 3.3$ $C(G13) = 4+1+4/3 = 3$ Thus, $C(G11) > C(G12) > C(G13)$
G14: Impact people's choices G15: Impact people's choices	$C(G14) = 1+3/2 = 2$ $C(G15) = 4+1/2 = 2.5$ Thus, $C(G15) > C(G14)$
G16: Create a "circle" of customers to chat with G17: Move messages from 3rd parties to spam folder	$C(G16) = 1+3/2 = 2$ $C(G17) = 4+1/2 = 2.5$ Thus, $C(G17) > C(G16)$
G18: Have secret chats G19: Listen to all voice messages G20: Read all the messages from all chats	$C(G18) = 1+5+5/3 = 3.6$ $C(G19) = 3+1+1/3 = 1.6$ $C(G20) = 5+1+1/3 = 2.3$ Thus, $C(G18) > C(G20) > C(G19)$
G21: Edit stories G22: See all messages/stories and etc. which have been edited	$C(G21) = 1+5/2 = 3$ $C(G22) = 3+1/2 = 4$ Thus, $C(G22) > C(G21)$
G23: Play all kinds of games and Integrate all browser games G24: Remove gaming feature G25: Restrict some games	$C(G23) = 1+3+4/3 = 2.6$ $C(G24) = 5+1+3/3 = 3$ $C(G25) = 5+1+1/3 = 2.3$ Thus, $C(G24) > C(G23) > C(G25)$
G26: Restrict some people from seeing any information related to me G27: Get all the detailed information about the person	$C(G26) = 1+3/2 = 2$ $C(G27) = 1+5/2 = 3$ Thus, $C(G27) > C(G26)$
G28: Delete others' messages G29: Constrain others from deleting my messages	$C(G28) = 1+3/2 = 2$ $C(G29) = 5+1/2 = 3$ Thus, $C(G29) > C(G28)$